

About Consciousness, Subtle Energies and Unification

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Abstract

In this paper we analyze the consciousness through a new structural model of energy we could call "General Gaussian Energy Group" (GGEG). By the infinite number of symmetry groups we recognize a series of new energy sources. We consider these ones as effective causes for fundamental consciousness. They would play an important role for consciousness (physical stuff with spirit stuff), explaining an individual material body system within a broader global system. The involved energy sources are SU(6), SU(12), SU(24), etc. This new structural model can be explained mathematically as follows: $SU(11) \supset SU(6) \times SU(5) \times U(1)$; $SU(23) \supset SU(12) \times SU(11) \times U(1)$; $SU(47) \supset SU(24) \times SU(23) \times U(1)$, etc, bringing to the creation of various new unknown particle-like entities in wave status, directly and indirectly linked to the creation of life, consciousness and other biological phenomena. The model, called B-DS model, is giving new answers to unsolved questions of reality. It is a new set of primary elements linked to the theory of quantum entanglement. These new structure is also particularly important for clarifications about subtle energies and about the deep vacuum structure.

Keywords: Consciousness; Subtle Energies; Unification; Entanglement; Vacuum Structure; B-DS Model; Mind Lensing

Introduction

It is well known that light with energy above a certain value can free electrons from a solid metal surface: it is the photoelectric effect. Each particle of light, called a photon, collides with an electron and uses some of its energy to remove the electron. The rest of the photon's energy transfers to the free negative charge, called a photoelectron [1]. Before Einstein, the effect had been observed by scientists, but they were confused about the behavior because the nature of light was not yet fully understood. In the late 1800s, also through the work of James Clerk Maxwell and Hendrik Lorentz, light appeared to behave as a wave. This was proven through the observation of light interference, diffraction and scattering, which are common to all sorts of waves.

The Einstein's argument in 1905 that light can also behave as set of particles was revolutionary because it did not fit with the classical theory of electromagnetic radiation;

Einstein was the first to fully elaborate the phenomenon with its implications. Heinrich Hertz saw the photoelectric effect in 1887, by sending ultraviolet light onto metal electrodes. In 1899, Joseph John Thompson demonstrated that ultraviolet light hitting a metal surface caused the ejection of electrons. A quantitative measure of the photoelectric effect came in 1902, with the work of Philipp Lenard. It was therefore clear that light had electrical properties, but the underlying mechanisms were not clear; later, Robert Millikan verified the Einstein's work [2]. Arthur Compton in 1922 showed that also X-rays could be treated as photons. Sometimes light seems to act as a wave, and sometimes as a particle [3].

Let us consider the analogy of the brain with photomultiplier tubes, with dynodes-like objects. Electrons are released after light strikes the cathodes of neuron electrodes. Electrons fall onto the first dynode-like, which releases more electrons falling on the second dynode-like, then on the third one, and so on. Each dynode-like amplifies

the current, until it is strong enough for the photomultipliers to detect even single photons.

We perceive the light as a continuous wave of electromagnetic radiation, but it is actually a stream of discrete particles. When a light ray starting by a point is propagated, the energy is not continuously distributed over an ever increasing volume, but it consists of a finite number of energy quanta, localized in space, which move without being divided and which can be absorbed or emitted only as a whole.

We can consider consciousness as created by the electromagnetic force in the framework of the group $SU(6) \times U(1)$. The human brain is conceived as an interfacing organ that receives information and hosts mind and consciousness. We can conceive the brain or parts of it as an *interference hologram* of incoming data and already existing ones, as *personal universe*.

A possible solution is to consider a global human being as an entity with the combination of two different characters of electromagnetic wave functions produced in two different phases by the symmetry breaking of $SU(11)$ and $SU(5)$ [4].

Subtle Energy and Consciousness

In previous papers it has been explained about the presence of new energy sources linked to the groups $SU(6)$, $SU(12)$, $SU(24)$, and so on [4-7].

Various studies have been carried out on the possible channels through which subtle energy appears to flow, and in relation to what type of physical energy flows through these channels, and about what type of particles. The presence of two subtle energy vectors has been hypothesized: *biophotons* and *bioelectrons*. Biophotons are photons generated inside the body and can be detected and measured as they emanate from the skin towards the outside of the body. Bioelectrons are present inside the body and can be detected and measured thanks to tools such as *electrophotonic imaging* [8].

Biophotonic emissions are extremely weak and cannot be observed with naked eye; the relative measurements require special photonic counters, sensitive to the point of tracking single photons. Biophotons are also associated with the *Qi* energy described in traditional Chinese medicine or with *Prana* described in Ayurveda and Yoga; taking part in the processes of biocommunication and biosignaling, there could be a complex interrelation between oxidative processes, biophotons and *Qi/Prana* energy [9-11].

Modern bio-field theory postulates electromagnetic interactions between cells, aimed at the control and transfer

of information, called *non-chemical and unconnected communications between cells and cells* [12].

It is known that the oxidative stress is a determining factor in many disorders of the metabolic syndrome, and it also seems to contribute to aging and the consequent degeneration of the body. It is likely that the emission of biophotons could be the protagonist of this fundamental process; it is thought to integrate the measurements of biophotons with those of the availability of electrons in biosystems, making this a simple and non-invasive method to measure the oxidative process in the body [13].

Modern science reveals that the basic unit of the body is the *cell*. The movement of cells follows the movement of the electrons inside them, which act according to their particular regular patterns; such electrons of the living body are called *bioelectrons* [14].

A bioelectronic disequilibrium involves cellular malfunction; Chinese medicine defines this as *disease*. External mechanical, physical, chemical and biological factors, and internal factors such as psychism, heredity, constitution, can cause a change in the bioelectrical movement of the body up to the disequilibrium that can cause disease.

Bioelectrons in the human body and photoelectric effects related to new energies connected to $SU(6)$, $SU(12)$, $SU(24)$ groups and similar can affect the human nervous system and/or human brain neurons, with the possible creation of pseudo-photoelectric currents, such as a system in active mode within a Wi-Fi region of a network-system like Earth within the Milky Way Galaxy. We assume that the process may be working like usable electrodes in the microtubules of the human brain neurons, flexibly controlled by the system of mind-consciousness, that could be named as *mind lensing*.

On Mind Lensing

We introduce the term *mind lensing* comparing with gravitational lensing in the case of photoelectric-like effects for the life or humans behaviours. Consciousness can be considered as integrated; this means that, although objects in consciousness have different qualities, we never experience each quality separately. We can think of a parallel between the effect of a gravitational lens for light and a similar effect of the mind for consciousness.

We think that consciousness may converge or bend by the electromagnetic interaction of mind-body system naturally or artificially exciting the nervous system through soft matter of biology and accelerated by the effect of photoelectric currents within the body.

We could consider a blue print, an architecture of the model of living matter atoms, considering the vacant spaces as filled with new energy sources of SU(6) as element of the theory of SU(11). Consciousness would result created by the series of new energy sources of SU(6), SU(12), SU(24), SU(48), etc in their respective frameworks of $SU(6) \times U(1)$, $SU(12) \times U(1)$, $SU(24) \times U(1)$, $SU(48) \times U(1)$, etc.

Individual humans or animals may use themselves as antenna in the broadcasting systems by gathering and strengthening their internal energies. The wave form of these new quanta of SU(11) are different from waves of matter of SU(5) of the physical universe.

On the Creation of Consciousness

Gravitational lensing happens when the light passes for example through a galaxy and it is bended because of gravitational field. To speak of light means to speak of packets of energy or photons.

Considering the Unified Gaussian Energy Group SU(11), beyond the Standard Model of Physics SU(5), we can consider the creation of various new unknown particles which contribute to the formation of consciousness.

There may be created packets of new energy by the energy groups of SU(6), SU(12), SU(24), etc, which are directly or indirectly linked to the formation of matter elements for the existences of life, consciousness, sense datum and other biological phenomena.

In this way it is possible to get new elements in the wave status of energies, linked to the theory of quantum entanglement and other peculiar properties of the vacuum. These new unknown energy packages become important for the discussion of the creation of consciousness [4-7].

In the theory of Gauss transformation in Physics, the special unitary group is used to represent bosonic symmetries; with theories with symmetry breaking, it is important to find the subgroups of the special unitary group. By the symmetry breaking of SU(11), we get SU(6) and SU(5), i.e. $SU(11) \supset SU(6) \times SU(5) \times U(1)$. Considering other unified groups with interlink between each other, we can discuss SU(23), SU(47), etc, in the similar manner of SU(11). In general, it holds: $SU(n) \supset SU(p) \times SU(n-p) \times U(1)$. Putting $p = 5$ and $n = 11$ (where $p > 1$ and $n - p > 1$), we get $SU(11) \supset SU(5) \times SU(6) \times U(1)$.

We assume that all various new unified groups SU(11), SU(23), SU(47), etc, are directly and indirectly responsible for non-living and as well as living matter world. The energies of SU(6) are expected to generate a latent energy,

such as SU(12), SU(24), etc, in their respective framework, participating in the creation of consciousness. We can recognize the essence of the architecture of the living matter in the vacuum as filled with these new energy sources and elements created by the bosons of the new energy sources. The combination of certain amount of unfolded new energies of SU(6), SU(12), SU(24), etc, will be then involved in the structure of consciousness.

Theories of great unification, having as basis groups like SU(5), seem not able to explain how consciousness arises in the universe. The series of new energy sources by SU(6), SU(12), SU(24), etc, with unknown particles, result involved in the understanding of consciousness, sense datum and biological phenomena [15].

Conclusion

The living status of human being is connected to a consciousness due to the creation of packages of various wavelengths derived by the different SU levels together with matter elements, bringing to biological phenomena like consciousness, emotions, sense datum, biological phenomena.

The analysis of phenomena as consciousness through this new structural model of energy recognizes a series of new energy sources as effective causes for fundamental consciousness. The model aims to clarify the status of consciousness, explaining an individual material body system within a broader global system. The involved energy sources are SU(6), SU(12), SU(24), and so on, bringing to the creation of various new unknown particle-like entities in wave status, linked to the creation of life, consciousness and other biological phenomena. This model is a new set of primary elements linked to quantum entanglement, deep structure of vacuum and subtle energies.

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